

Local Government in India

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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Local Responsibilities and Public Services

2.1. Local Responsibilities and Public Services in India: An Introduction

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The Ministry of Housing and Urban Affairs (MoHUA) and the Ministry of *Panchayati Raj* (MoPR) are responsible for urban and rural local governments, respectively. For the efficient delivery of services and to oversee civic affairs, various reforms have been introduced to strengthen the work of urban local governments. These reforms are introduced from time to time by successive governments in power. These various reforms are decentralization of authority, power, functions and finances to lower levels of government. This leads to democratic decentralization of local governments providing them greater autonomy in their everyday functions and duties.

The Ministry of Housing and Urban Affairs (MoHUA) is responsible for the holistic development of urban areas and it primarily looks over issues of governance and infrastructure. One of the major responsibilities of MoHUA has been the reform of public services so as to ensure the smooth functioning of the projects and their sustainability once they are completed. Two prominent urban missions are Atal Mission for Rejuvenation and Urban Transformation (AMRUT) which is responsible for urban planning, implementation and governance for improving service delivery and the *Pradhan Mantri Awas Yojana* (PMAY) which is an initiative to ensure affordable housing for all. Missions mean initiatives and projects that have clearly defined objectives, timeline for their completion, set targets, expected outcomes and delivery mechanisms well in place before the completion of the missions.

The State Municipal Acts govern the urban local governments and each state has its own municipal act. The central government directs the states to enact the municipal acts so that the framework, functions and power can be assigned to the local urban governments. The basic structure of the act is the same; however, it varies from state to state depending upon the state in question and the local government. The variation in the provisions of the Municipal Acts depends on the size of the state, population of the state, and also depends on the socio-economic activities of the state.⁷

According to the 73rd and 74th constitutional amendment acts, there are compulsory and voluntary provisions which have to be followed by the state governments, while formulating their own local self-government acts. These variations could be related to subjects like the

⁷ For example, the Municipal Corporation of Delhi provides civic amenity services to both the rural and urban areas, whereas the Chennai Municipal Corporation services only the urban areas. To elaborate further, Delhi's rural areas have been rapidly urbanized and the need for rural classification was negated in the year 1989.

constitutional provisions related to the reservations for scheduled castes, scheduled tribes and women.

Municipalities have the power to draft by-laws for better implementation of administrative functions. The various responsibilities and provision of public services by local urban bodies are public health and sanitation, medical relief, public works, education, development and administration.

Local governments are solely responsible for the delivery of services to a range of citizens with the collaboration of various organizations. These could be voluntary organizations, self-help groups of various kinds funded by the government or non-government organizations funded privately or through large national and international organizations and donor agencies.

The national and state level governments have also started smart cities initiatives which consider the use of information and communication technologies (ICTs) and use of special purpose vehicles (SPVs). Smart Cities programs focus on the central role of local government as important decision makers in implementing projects based on planning and growth of cities and their connectivity issues pertaining to the road and transport infrastructure. This involves connecting rural and urban cities and towns through projects like National Highway Authority of India (NHAI).

The rural local governments have the same structure except in scheduled and tribal areas which are legally exempted from the implementation of the *Panchayati Raj Act*. The *Panchayat Extension to Scheduled Areas (PESA) Act*, 1996 with few modifications is also applicable in tribal areas. Regional or district councils have been mandated to officiate work and protect indigenous customs and traditions.

Local responsibilities and public services differ from state to state. The fundamental responsibilities and services that the state is responsible for is the provision of infrastructure facilities like the sanitation, management of waste, building of roads and public conveniences, projects to alleviate poverty and distress, economic development and growth. At the grass root level, it involves participation from the local communities, especially women. Programs involving the community participation like the National Rural Livelihood Mission (NRLM) have been to some extent a success.

To achieve the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the central government started – with a role of the states in implementation – the National Institution for Transforming India (NITI) which was responsible for the completion of seventeen SDGs in August 2017 including a wide range of responsibilities for Urban Development and *Panchayat Raj* Ministries., the latter dealing with the local self-government in the rural areas administered under the Ministry of Local Self-Government known as *panchayati raj* as stated above.

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